

Prediction of directivity characteristics of piezoelectric macro-fiber composite interdigital transducers: a semi-analytical approach

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Abstract. The employment of guided waves for structural health monitoring applications has attracted substantial attention in recent years. Piezoelectric transducers are frequently employed in these systems for elastic wave generation and acquisition. Their dynamic properties, i.e., direction-dependent frequency characteristics such as directivity patterns, are an important feature for designing a reliable monitoring strategy. Although analysis of the transducer directivity pattern can be performed using finite element models, these usually tend to be computationally very expensive, especially for parametric and optimization studies.

In this paper, a semi-analytical framework is proposed that can predict the far-field directivity patterns of complex transducers of arbitrary shape and structure mounted on a substrate. The framework described in this paper integrates analytical far-field predictions with a local finite element model evaluating the traction field produced by the transducer. Consequently, the FE model accurately captures near-field responses, whereas the analytical component predicts the far-field responses.

The implementation of this semi-analytical framework requires the development of analytical and numerical approaches. The former includes computation of dispersion curves of the inspected plate, the stress and displacement profiles of wave modes, and ultimately, the excitability relations, while the latter includes estimation of the traction field between the transducer and the plate using the FE model. Owing to the popularity of piezoelectric macro-fiber composite (MFC) transducers, in this paper, we apply the proposed method to predict the directivity patterns of MFC M2807-P2 transducer. To validate the reliability of the proposed method, the predicted patterns are compared with experimental results obtained using Laser Doppler Vibrometer.

Keywords: structural health monitoring, guided waves, piezoelectric transducers, interdigital transducers, macro-fiber composites, directivity predictions

Introduction

The utilization of guided wave based structural health monitoring (SHM) has garnered significant interest over the past two decades owing to their high sensitivity to defects and ability of scanning large areas [1, 2]. These SHM strategies frequently employ piezoelectric transducers for the generation of ultrasonic guided waves. In recent times, owing to the advantages of being lightweight and flexible, macro-fiber composite (MFC) transducers are popularly used for the generation of guided waves in SHM applications [3, 4]. MFC transducers provide easy integration through gluing or embedding within large and intricate structures, without causing surface damage. Additionally, they can be readily coupled with various contact and non-contact inspection methods for SHM of structures [5].

Due to the multi-modal and dispersive nature of guided waves, the dynamic characteristics of MFC transducers, particularly their direction-dependent frequency characteristics, play a crucial role in formulating reliable SHM methodologies. In particular, the *a priori* knowledge of the transducers' directivity patterns assists in estimating the optimal quantity and arrangement/positions of MFC transducers needed for monitoring extensive and intricate structures [6]. Moreover, a thorough understanding of these directivity patterns is vital for selecting the excitation frequency and subsequently determining the utilized wave mode(s) in the monitoring analysis.

Although finite element (FE) models are capable of predicting the directivity patterns of transducers, they often incur high computational costs, rendering them impractical for parametric and optimization studies. Thus, the development of analytical and semi-analytical approaches for directivity patterns' predictions of piezoelectric transducers is gaining popularity. In [7], a formulation for modeling guided wave field excited by surface-bonded piezoelectric transducers of arbitrary shape on isotropic plates was reported. In [8], the approach reported in [7] was extended to develop a semi-analytical approach wherein a local FE model is coupled with analytical far-field solutions of the plate response to predict far-field directivity patterns of MFC transducers mounted on isotropic plates. More recently, an analytical model for directivity predictions of MFC transducer mounted on isotropic plate was reported in [6]. All these reported studies, however, assume the transducer to be homogenized. Such type of modeling, especially for an MFC transducer comprises an arrangement of piezoelectric and non-piezoelectric fibers, restricts the model's ability to be used for optimization studies related to the transducer's structure.

In this paper, we outline a novel general semi-analytical framework capable of predicting the far-field transmission directivity patterns of complex transducers of arbitrary shape and structure mounted on a substrate. This framework comprises numerical and analytical approaches that are coupled together. The former consists of a local FE model capturing the near field effects while the latter, based on the numerically predicted results, predicts the far-field responses of the transducer-substrate setup. The framework proposed here is very versatile and general, and thence, not restricted to any specific numerical methods. In this work, we have employed the proposed framework to predict the directivity patterns of MFC M2807-P2 transducer mounted on an elastic isotropic plate. Unlike the previous reported studies in [7, 8], the MFC transducer was modeled with an exact topology.

The paper is structured as follows: firstly, we introduce the semi-analytical framework, explaining its numerical and analytical components. Next, we briefly discuss the various methodologies employed in both the numerical and analytical sections. Following that, we predict the directivity pattern of the MFC M2807-P2 transducer mounted on an aluminum plate of 2 mm thickness using the proposed semi-analytical framework and experimental studies. Finally, we draw conclusions.

1. Semi-analytical framework for directivity pattern predictions

The semi-analytical framework proposed in this paper predicts the far-field displacement responses of complex piezoelectric transducers mounted on a substrate. The former can be of any shape and structure, while the latter can have any degree of anisotropy and inhomogeneity. The semi-analytical framework consists of two approaches, namely, numerical and analytical, as shown in Fig. 1. The numerical approach requires a local FE model that implements the piezo-electromechanical coupling between the transducer and the substrate, and the analytical approach uses the FE model results as an input to predict the far-field displacement responses. In particular, the numerical approach addresses all the near-field couplings/effects.

The analytical approach of the framework consists of two sub-frameworks, while the numerical part, as mentioned previously, consists of an FE model, as shown in Fig. 1. To predict the far-field responses, first, the far-field Green's function of the substrate is required to be determined. Note that the far-field Green's function is given by the spectral properties (i.e., dispersion and the excitability characteristics) of the substrate [9]. Subsequently, the spectral properties are integrated with the inputs from the FE model (numerical approach) to determine the far-field responses, as shown in Fig. 1. It is important to emphasize that any methodologies or techniques may be applied within the analytical and numerical components of the framework, provided that the handling of inputs and outputs aligns with the representation depicted in Fig. 1. Consequently, the proposed semi-analytical framework is highly versatile and not confined to any particular methods. In this paper, the viability of the proposed semi-analytical framework is demonstrated by employing it for far-field directivity patterns' predictions of MFC transducer mounted on an elastic isotropic plate of 2 mm thickness. The different methodologies employed in this paper for the analytical and numerical parts of the framework (Fig. 1) are briefly discussed below.

Fig. 1. Semi-analytical framework for far-field response (directivity patterns') predictions of piezoelectric transducer-substrate setup.

1.1 Computation of the far-field Green's function

The computation of the far-field Green's function of the substrate necessitates determining the respective dispersion curves followed by the stress and displacement profiles, and ultimately, the excitability characteristics. Consequently, in this study, assuming an infinite plate on which the MFC transducer is mounted, we utilized the stiffness matrix method (SMM) [10, 11] for the computation of dispersion relations. The SMM was chosen due to its reported computational efficiency and reliability [11]. Subsequently, we developed an

algorithm based on SMM that is capable of predicting the dispersion curves of anisotropic plates with arbitrary material properties.

In SMM, the displacements and stresses at the top and bottom free surfaces of a plate are related as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\}_0 \\ \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\}_h \end{Bmatrix} = \mathbf{K} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\mathbf{u}\}_0 \\ \{\mathbf{u}\}_h \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and \mathbf{u} denote the displacement and stress vectors, respectively, at the top (0) and bottom (h) surfaces of the plate, and \mathbf{K} represents the stiffness matrix comprising a pair of frequency (ω) and wavenumber (k) (or, velocity (v)). Further details regarding the composition of \mathbf{K} can be found in [11].

Assuming stress-free boundary conditions at the top and bottom surfaces, Eq. (1) becomes

$$0 = \mathbf{K} \begin{Bmatrix} \{\mathbf{u}\}_0 \\ \{\mathbf{u}\}_h \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) presents an eigenvalue problem, wherein the solution pairs (ω, k) denote the dispersion relations, and the eigenvectors give the displacements at the top and bottom surfaces of the plate. It should be noted that the implementation of multilayered setups is also achievable through the utilization of the recursive algorithm outlined in reference [12]. Utilizing these displacements, the through-thickness profiles of displacement and stress fields are calculated by using the list of equations/formulas provided in [13].

Finally, the excitability relations are computed by utilizing the normal mode expansion method [14], wherein the excitability is determined for each wavemode at a specified frequency, ω . Consequently, the n^{th} wavemode's far-field excitability, a_n , owing to a harmonic point source (with ω frequency) located at the surface h of plate is given as

$$a_n = \frac{i\omega \mathbf{u}_n^*(h) \cdot \mathbf{F}}{4P_{nn}}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{F} and $\mathbf{u}_n(h)$ are the harmonic point force and displacement vectors, respectively, at the surface h of the plate, the superscript * denotes conjugation, and P_{ij} is the energy flux between the wavemodes i and j. Then, the excited wavemode's displacement vector at an observation point (x_1, x_2) located at the surface of the plate is given as

$$\mathbf{U}_n(x_1, x_2) = a_n \mathbf{u}_n(h) e^{i\mathbf{k}_n \cdot \mathbf{x}}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{k}_n is the wavevector of the n^{th} wavemode and \mathbf{x} is the vector between the excitation and observation points.

Using the procedure outlined above, the dispersion relations, followed by the displacement and stress profiles, and the out-of-plane excitability characteristics were determined for an aluminum plate of 2 mm thickness. Figure 2 presents the computed dispersion and excitability characteristics up to a frequency of 200 kHz.

Fig. 2. Dispersion (a) and excitability (b) characteristics of aluminum plate of 2 mm thickness computed using the procedure outlined in Sec. 1.1.

1.2 Finite element modeling

The primary aim of this sub-framework is to assess the traction field produced by the transducer acting on the plate. Evaluating the resultant traction necessitates an approach that integrates mechanical and electrostatic domains, thereby requiring a multi-physics methodology. Consequently, any FEM solver capable of managing multi-physics complexities can be utilized.

In this study we model the exact topology of the MFC M2807 transducer. Developing an exact model provides the advantage of its potential utilization in design and optimization studies. Consequently, the piezoelectric transducer was modeled as shown in Fig. 3(a). The dimensions of the transducer were 28 (along x_2) x 7 (along x_1) x 0.18 (along x_3) mm. Note the implementation of the perfectly match layer (PML) at the edges of the plate to minimize the interference of boundary-reflected waves.

Fig. 3. (a) Modeled MFC M2807-P2 transducer-plate setup with PML at the boundaries. (b) Close up view of the modeled MFC M2807-P2 transducer showing the PZT and epoxy fibers arranged parallel to each other.

The transducer is composed of lead zirconate titanate (PZT) and epoxy fibers aligned parallel to each other along the x_2 direction, as illustrated in Fig. 3(b). The dimensions of the aluminum plate, PZT (PZT-5A) and epoxy fibers employed in the analysis are provided in Tab. 1. The material properties of the PZT and epoxy fibers are presented in Tab. 2. The

dimensions and material properties of the fibers were provided by *Smart Material Corp.* Due to the varying widths of the PZT and epoxy fibers within the transducer, a non-uniform mesh distribution was used for the transducer, and consequently, for the interface between the transducer and the plate. Hexahedral mesh elements were adopted while ensuring that their sizes remained within the constraints of stability and numerical Brillouin zone limitations [15, 16].

Table 1. Dimensions of the geometries in the FEM model

Modeled geometry	Length (along x2) [mm]	Length (along x1) [mm]	Thickness (along x3) [mm]
PZT fiber	28	0.53	0.18
Epoxy fiber	28	0.055	0.18
Aluminum plate	50	50	2

Table 2. Material properties of PZT-5A and epoxy fibers used in the FEM model.

PZT- 5A	$C_{11}^E = 1.20 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $C_{22}^E = 1.20 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $C_{33}^E = 1.11 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $C_{12}^E = 0.75 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $C_{13}^E = 0.75 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $C_{23}^E = 0.75 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $C_{44}^E = 0.21 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $C_{55}^E = 0.21 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $C_{66}^E = 0.22 \times 10^{11}$ Pa; $e_{31} = -5.35$ C/m ² ; $e_{33} = 15.78$ C/m ² ; $e_{32} = -5.35$ C/m ² ; $e_{24} = 12.29$ C/m ² ; $e_{15} = 12.24$ C/m ² ; $\rho = 7700$ kg/m ³ ; $\epsilon_{11}^T = 919.1$; $\epsilon_{22}^T = 919.1$; $\epsilon_{33}^T = 826.6$;		
Epoxy	$E = 3 \times 10^9$ Pa; $\rho = 1150$ kg/m ³ ; $\nu = 0.42$;		

The excitation was achieved by applying electric potential and ground boundary conditions to the transducer. Subsequently, the traction field was acquired by performing harmonic (frequency domain) simulations at 100 kHz.

1.3 The integration procedure

The integration sub-framework is tasked with coupling the spectral properties of the isotropic plate (computed in Sec. 1.1) and the traction field generated at the MFC transducer-plate setup (computed in Sec. 1.2) to predict the far-field directivity patterns of the transducer. In this paper, we have employed the Gaussian quadrature method for integration wherein the FE traction field evaluated at the integration (Gauss) points of the FE model was used. Employing this integration technique, the out-of-plane displacements at multiple observation points, arranged in a circular pattern around the transducer, were computed to predict the directivity pattern. These points were positioned at a distance of 100 mm from the transducer's center, as shown in Fig. 4(a).

In the following section, the far-field directivity patterns predicted by the semi-analytical framework outlined above and the experimental studies are compared.

2. Directivity pattern of Macro Fiber Composite Transducer – Experimental Validation

The experimental studies were performed using the Polytec PSV-400 scanning laser vibrometer (Polytec GmbH Polytec-Platz 1-7, Waldbronn, Germany). The MFC M2807-P2 transducer (supplied by *Smart Material Corp.*) was mounted on top of a 1000 x 1000 x 2 mm aluminum plate using a double-sided adhesive tape and the out-of-plane responses (velocities) were measured using the vibrometer. To enhance the reflective characteristics of the surface and achieve more precise outcomes, the region targeted for measurement wave

exposure was coated with a retroreflective material specifically designed for laser vibrometer testing. A cutout matching the dimensions of the transducer was created to facilitate direct bonding of the transducer onto the plate. The transducer was excited by a Hamming-window modulated nine-cycle sinusoidal tone burst signal of frequency 100 kHz, and the sampling frequency of the vibrometer was set to 3.125 MHz. Subsequently, analogous to the semi-analytical framework, the out-of-plane responses were measured by the vibrometer at several points around the transducer forming a circle, as shown in Fig. 4(a), to estimate the directivity pattern.

The experimental studies gave velocity data, whereas the semi-analytical framework provided displacement responses. Consequently, the displacement responses obtained from the semi-analytical framework were converted into velocity responses by multiplying them with the term $i\omega$ [14]. Figure 4(b) shows the normalized directivity patterns of the out-of-plane (velocity) responses of the MFC M2807-P2 transducer, acquired through the semi-analytical framework and experimental investigations, using a 100 kHz excitation. It can be observed from Fig. 4(b) that the directivity patterns predicted by the semi-analytical framework are clearly consistent with the patterns obtained from experimental studies. This alignment validates the semi-analytical framework proposed in this paper. As anticipated, the experimental directivity patterns exhibit slight discrepancies compared to their simulated counterparts due to the non-harmonic nature of the excitation during experiments, resulting in the presence of frequencies other than the excitation frequency in the recorded responses. It is important to note that the semi-analytical results were derived under purely harmonic excitation conditions. Additionally, while the results from the semi-analytical method display symmetry, the experimental results exhibit slight asymmetry owing to imperfect bonding between the transducer and the plate.

Fig. 4. (a) Illustration of the observation points around the MFC M2807-P2 transducer, where the out-of-plane responses were predicted (via the semi-analytical framework) and recorded (through experimental studies). (b) The directivity patterns of the out-of-plane response for the MFC M2807-P2 transducer obtained by the semi-analytical framework and experimental studies at 100 kHz excitation.

Conclusion

This paper introduces a novel and versatile semi-analytical framework capable of predicting the far-field directivity patterns of complex transducers mounted on substrates. Unlike existing approaches that are limited to homogenized MFC transducers, this framework accommodates transducers of arbitrary shape and structure, including various compositions and material properties, enhancing its versatility. The framework consists of multiple

constituent sub-frameworks, each adaptable to different schemes or methods, thus offering great flexibility and generality.

To demonstrate the utility of the proposed framework, we employ it to forecast the far-field directivity patterns of an MFC M2807-P2 transducer mounted on a 2 mm thick aluminum plate. Experimental studies are conducted to validate the predictions of the semi-analytical framework, revealing agreement between the predicted and experimentally obtained directivity patterns.

This framework has a general character, and its applications enable straightforward determination of the optimal operational frequency or wavelength for any transducer. Additionally, it facilitates optimization studies, allowing for the exploration of parameters such as size, shape, material properties, composition, and bonding type for single or multiple transducers configured with the substrate, tailored to specific requirements.

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